

CONSTITUTIVE MODEL OF COMPOSITE ELECTRIC CONDUCTORS BY FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

J. T. Tzeng¹ and W. Sun²

¹ *US Army Research Laboratory, AMSRL-WM-MB, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD 21005, U.S.A.*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering and Mechanics, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA 19104, U.S.A.*

SUMMARY: Finite element approaches to predict the effective mechanical properties of a composite conductor in an electrical machine are presented. The effective constants of conductor (nine in total) are calculated with a combined analytical and finite element technique for a representative volume. It is noted that the mechanical properties of the electrical composite conductor are difficult to be determined by experimental methods. The approach enables the use of a global-local analytical method for electrical machine design with complex geometry and material composition. The results from the global analysis can then be interoperated at the local/detail level for the evaluation of potential failure mechanism.

KEYWORDS: Micromechanics, finite element methods, composites, homogenization, composite conductor

INTRODUCTION

Electrical machinery, which ranges from electric drive vehicles to electric weapons, could be a critical component for future combat systems. Compact, durable, and highly mobile power generators and motors are necessary for the success of all electrical systems. Because of the complex conductor winding geometry and the heterogeneity of the conductor and composite insulation, electrical machinery is usually analyzed with numerical techniques, of which, the finite element method is most widely used. However, a standard finite element analysis that runs even on a modern large capacity computer cannot efficiently analyze each structural entity from the whole machine system. Therefore, each structural entity must be analyzed separately at the global and local levels. The analyses conducted at the global level use the homogenized effective properties derived from the representative volume element (RVE) in Figure 1. In this level, the structure of the composite conductor is homogenized by the smearing of the distinctive phases of constituents into an RVE and with the RVE's effective properties representing the composite conductor and the global responses of the composite conductor to predict the service loading. The results derived from the global analysis will then be used to conduct the local level analysis. Accordingly, the detail stress, strain, and energy fields will be calculated and used to predict the structural integrity, performance, and service life under the service loading of the.

The objective of this study is to develop a finite element modeling technique to predict the effective mechanical properties of composite electrical conductor, thus to validate the previously developed analytical homogeneous modeling [1, 2]. The models were formulated

based on the micromechanics modeling technique [3-5]. This approach is also extended to calculate the detail stress and strain profile in the conductor and in the insulating layers with a global-local analytical technique. Since the analysis is performed at a local level, mechanical, thermal, and electromagnetic loading conditions can all be included, even with consideration of thermal degradation of mechanical properties. This report summarizes the development of the finite element modeling and the numerical approach to calculate the effective mechanical properties of developed composite electrical conductor.

LAYOUT OF COMPOSITE CONDUCTOR AND HOMOGENIZATION MODEL

The structural layout of the developed EM composite conductor consists of an interior conducting metal core, the enclosing insulation shell, and a circular cavity through the middle of the core. The aluminum core conducts pulsating electric currents that can cause rapid heating of the core material. The outer insulation shell is composed of the layers of polymer insulation, and plain woven glass-fiber composite. The fiber-reinforced polymer composite is used in the insulation because of the desirable mechanical and thermal properties, as well as an extra insulating protection. The small cavity in the middle of the core lets a pressurized coolant circulate at a high velocity in order to reduce the heat. The conductor core with cooling channel, wrapped with the insulating composites, is packed into a winding assembly. The section geometry and the phase materials are shown schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematics of composite conductor RVE and homogenization modeling approach.

Because of the different fiber orientations of the overlapped composite in the composite conductor global coordinate system, we model the insulation layer as two different insulation composite blocks: 1) at the horizontal surfaces, denoted as CB1, and 2) at the vertical surfaces, denoted as CB2. The difference between CB1 and CB2 is in the fiber orientation of the

composite with respect to the global coordinate system XYZ, as shown in Figure 2. The effective properties of the insulation composite block CB1 and CB2 can be calculated with the micro-mechanics model proposed [1, 2] and illustrated in Table 1.

Figure 2: Section views of conductor and insulation composite blocks

Table 1. Homogenized elastic mechanical properties for composite insulation blocks.

Composite insulation Block CB1	Composite insulation Block CB2
$E^{CB1}_{XX} = 1.0 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E^{CB2}_{XX} = 0.236 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$E^{CB1}_{YY} = 0.236 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E^{CB2}_{YY} = 1.0 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$E^{CB1}_{ZZ} = 1.0 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E^{CB2}_{ZZ} = 1.0 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G^{CB1}_{XY} = 0.092 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G^{CB2}_{XY} = 0.092 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G^{CB1}_{YZ} = 0.092 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G^{CB2}_{XZ} = 0.71 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G^{CB1}_{XZ} = 0.71 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G^{CB2}_{YZ} = 0.092 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$\nu^{CB1}_{XY} = 0.073$	$\nu^{CB2}_{XY} = 0.31$
$\nu^{CB1}_{YZ} = 0.31$	$\nu^{CB2}_{YZ} = 0.38$
$\nu^{CB1}_{XZ} = 0.38$	$\nu^{CB2}_{XZ} = 0.31$

FEA MODELING AND NUMERICAL CALCULATION

The finite element model is developed based on the basis of designed CAD model geometry. The FEA software used in the analysis is ANSYS. As shown in Figure 3, a total of 6,300 eight-node brick elements was generated in ANSYS for the RVE CAD model represented in the figure. Out of the 6,300 elements, there are 1,260 eight-node Solid64 type structural anisotropic elements in CB1, 1,440 eight-node Solid64 type structural anisotropic elements in CB2, and 3,600 eight-node Solid45 type structural brick elements in the aluminum core. The

material properties of CB1 and CB2 are taken from Table 1, and the core property is assumed to be aluminum.

Figure 3: The approach - from CAD model to FEA model.

Effective Young's Modulus

A schematic illustration for applying boundary and loading conditions for numerical calculation of effective constant E_{XX} is shown in Figure 4. As shown in the figure, we apply a uniform displacement field $U_X = 0.001L_X$, which is equivalent to $\epsilon_X = 0.1\%$, on the surface S_{X1} , and we apply the constraint, $U_X = 0.0$, on the surface S_{X2} . This boundary condition is intended to produce a uniform displacement field within the FEA model. The effective constant E_{XX} can be calculated from following equation:

$$E_{XX} = \frac{\sigma_X}{\epsilon_X} = \frac{\left(\frac{R_X}{A_{SX2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{U_X}{L_X}\right)} = 0.001 \times \frac{R_X}{A_{SX2}} \quad (1)$$

With: $U_X = 0.001L_X$ On S_{X1}
 $U_X = 0.0$ On S_{X2}

in which A_{SX1} and A_{SX2} are the areas of the surface S_{X1} and S_{X2} , respectively, L_X is the dimension of the RVE in X direction, and R_X is the X-component of the average reaction force produced on that surface S_{X2} caused by the applied displacement U_X on surface S_{X1} .

The FEA predicted displacement field d_X and stress field σ_X subjected to the applying boundary condition and loading are displayed in Figure 5(a). As shown in the figure, a uniform displacement field is observed near the surfaces S_{X1} and S_{X2} in X direction. Away from the surfaces and close to the cooling channel, the displacement field is no longer uniform. Stress

concentrations are predicted along the circumference of the cooling channel. The contour representations for strain field and for von Mises stress field are presented in Figure 5(b).

Figure 4: Loading and boundary condition in determining effective Young's modulus E_{XX} .

Figure 5: Contour representations of displacement d_x and stress field σ_x (E_{XX} calculation).

A computer code was written to adapt the output of ANSYS analysis and calculate the elastic modulus, E_{XX} based on Equation 1.

Analogically, this numerical approach can also be applied to calculate the effective Young's modulus E_{YY} and E_{ZZ} through the following mathematical formulations:

$$E_{YY} = \frac{\sigma_Y}{\epsilon_Y} = \frac{\left(\frac{R_Y}{A_{SY2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{U_Y}{L_Y}\right)} = 0.001 \times \frac{R_Y}{A_{SY2}} \quad (2)$$

With: $U_Y = 0.001L_X$ On S_{Y1}
 $U_Y = 0.0$ On S_{Y2}

and

$$E_{ZZ} = \frac{\sigma_Z}{\varepsilon_Z} = \frac{\left(\frac{R_Z}{A_{SZ2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{U_Z}{L_Z}\right)} = 0.001 \times \frac{R_Z}{A_{SZ2}} \quad (3)$$

with:

$$U_Z = 0.001L_Z \quad \text{On } S_{Z1}$$

$$U_Z = 0.0 \quad \text{On } S_{Z2}$$

in which A_{SY2} is the area of the surface S_{Y2} in Y direction, A_{SZ2} is the area of the surface S_{Z2} in Z direction, L_Y and L_Z are the RVE dimension in Y and in Z, and R_Y and R_Z are the Y-component and Z-component of the average resultant reaction force produced on the S_{Y2} surface and S_{Z2} surface, respectively.

As a parametric study, we applied different uniform displacement fields U_X in the E_{XX} calculation to verify the sensitivity of the FEA model to the imposed displacements. The FEA results are presented in Figure 6. As shown in the figure, the FEA predicted E_{XX} seems to be insensitive to the applied displacement. For all four different U_X values (i.e., $U_X = 1L_X$, $0.1L_X$, $0.01L_X$, and $0.001L_X$), E_{XX} values are predicted nearly as a constant: $E_{XX} = 1.94 \times 10^6$ (psi).

Figure 6: Prediction of E_{XX} under different displacement field U_X ($E_{XX} = 1.94 \times 10^6$ psi).

Effective Shear Modulus

A schematic illustration for applying boundary and loading condition for numerical calculation of effective share modulus G_{XY} is shown in Figure 7. As shown in the figure, we apply a uniform displacement field $U_X = 0.001L_Y$, which is equivalent to $\gamma_{XY} = 0.1\%$, on the top surface S_{Y1} , and constrain $U_X = 0.0$ on the bottom surface S_{Y2} . In order to ensure that a pure shear deformation can be produced in the model, we also apply a constraint $U_Y = 0.0$ on both left and right surface, S_{X1} and S_{X2} , respectively.

The effective constant G_{XY} can be calculated from following equation:

$$G_{XY} = \frac{\sigma_{XY}}{\gamma_{XY}} = \frac{\left(\frac{R_X}{A_{SY2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{U_X}{L_Y}\right)} = 0.001 \times \frac{R_X}{A_{SY2}} \quad (4)$$

with:

$$U_X = 0.001L_Y \quad \text{on } S_{Y1}$$

$$U_X = 0.0 \quad \text{on } S_{Y2}$$

$$U_Y = 0.0 \quad \text{on } S_{X1} \text{ and } S_{X2}$$

in which A_{SY2} is the area of the surface S_{Y2} and R_X is the X-component of the average reaction force produced on the surface S_{Y2} caused by the applied displacement U_X on surface S_{Y1}

Figure 7: Loading and boundary condition in determining G_{XY} .

The FEA-predicted displacement field d_X , shear strain field γ_{XY} , and shear stress field σ_{XY} , subjected to the applied boundary conditions and loadings are displayed in Figures 8 and 9, respectively.

Figure 8: Contour representations of displacement field d_X (in G_{XY} calculation).

a) Shear strain field γ_{XY}
@ $U_X = 0.001$

b) Shear stress field σ_{XY}
@ $U_X = 0.001$

Figure 9: Contour representations of shear strain field γ_{XY} and shear stress field σ_{XY} (in G_{XY} calculation).

A computer code was written to adapt the output of ANSYS analysis and calculate the shear modulus, G_{XY} , based on Equation 4.

Analogically, this numerical approach can also be applied to calculate the effective shear modulus G_{YZ} and G_{XZ} through the following formulations:

$$G_{YZ} = \frac{\sigma_{YZ}}{\gamma_{YZ}} = \frac{\left(\frac{R_Z}{A_{SY2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{U_Z}{L_Y}\right)} = 0.001 \times \frac{R_Z}{A_{SY2}} \quad (5)$$

with:

$$U_Z = 0.001L_Y \quad \text{on } S_{Y1}$$

$$U_Z = 0.0 \quad \text{on } S_{Y2}$$

$$U_Y = 0.0 \quad \text{on both } S_{Z1} \text{ and } S_{Z2}$$

and

$$G_{XZ} = \frac{\sigma_{XZ}}{\gamma_{XZ}} = \frac{\left(\frac{R_X}{A_{SZ2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{U_X}{L_Z}\right)} = 0.001 \times \frac{R_X}{A_{SZ2}} \quad (6)$$

with:

$$U_X = 0.001L_Z \quad \text{on } S_{Z1}$$

$$U_X = 0.0 \quad \text{on } S_{Z2}$$

$$U_Z = 0.0 \quad \text{on both } S_{X1} \text{ and } S_{X2}$$

The FEA predicted displacement field, shear strain field, and shear stress field subjected to the above boundary condition and loading for G_{YZ} and G_{XZ} calculation are not displayed because of limited pages available.

Effective Poisson Ratios

Calculations for Poisson ratios are based on following equations:

$$\nu_{XY} = -\frac{\varepsilon_{YY}}{\varepsilon_{XX}} \quad (7)$$

$$\nu_{YZ} = -\frac{\varepsilon_{ZZ}}{\varepsilon_{YY}} \quad (8)$$

$$\nu_{XZ} = -\frac{\varepsilon_{ZZ}}{\varepsilon_{XX}} \quad (9)$$

in which ε_{ij} , $ij = X, Y,$ and Z , are the numerical results predicted from the FEA models. The results of the Poisson ratios are summarized in next section.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section summarizes the results of the numerical calculations of the nine mechanical constants predicted from the FEA models. Comparisons of the numerical results with the analytical model predictions [1, 2] are also presented. The application of the FEA model to conductors with different cross sections of the aluminum core with and without the cooling channel and the comparison of the numerical prediction with the analytical prediction are also presented. A summary of the FEA predictions for a conductor with cooling channel is listed in Table 2 for an aluminum core with cross section of 750 x 920 mils, and Table 3 for an aluminum core with cross section of 750 x 750 mils. For a comparison, the results of the predictions from the analytical model [16] are also listed in the tables.

Table 2: Mechanical constants of conductor with cooling channel: Numerical and analytical predictions (for aluminum core 750 x 920 x 1).

Numerical Prediction	Analytical Prediction
$E_{XX}^{FEA} = 1.94 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E_{XX}^{ANA} = 2.07 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$E_{YY}^{FEA} = 2.20 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E_{YY}^{ANA} = 2.40 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$E_{ZZ}^{FEA} = 7.63 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E_{ZZ}^{ANA} = 7.64 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G_{XY}^{FEA} = 0.478 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G_{XY}^{ANA} = 0.495 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G_{YZ}^{FEA} = 0.887 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G_{XZ}^{ANA} = 0.843 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G_{XZ}^{FEA} = 0.775 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G_{YZ}^{ANA} = 0.738 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$\nu_{XY}^{FEA} = 0.412$	$\nu_{XY}^{ANA} = 0.341$
$\nu_{YZ}^{FEA} = 0.313$	$\nu_{YZ}^{ANA} = 0.324$
$\nu_{XZ}^{FEA} = 0.321$	$\nu_{XZ}^{ANA} = 0.322$

From the results and comparison presented in Tables 2 and 3, we observed a close agreement between the FEA and the analytical predictions for all effective constants, particularly for six modulus and two out-of-the-plane Poisson ratios. The largest difference between the two

predictions was the in-plane Poisson ratios. It is believed the value of the FEA prediction might be slightly higher. The good agreements between the numerical and analytical predictions prove the applicability of both the FEA modeling approach and homogenous modeling approach for the EM composite conductor. This is particularly important since the mechanical properties of the electrical composite conductor are relatively difficult to be determined by testing methods.

Table 3: Mechanical constants of conductor with cooling channel: Numerical and analytical predictions (for aluminum core 750 x 750 x 1).

Numerical Prediction	Analytical Prediction
$E_{XX}^{FEA} = 1.90 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E_{XX}^{ANA} = 2.02 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$E_{YY}^{FEA} = 1.90 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E_{YY}^{ANA} = 2.02 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$E_{ZZ}^{FEA} = 7.33 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$E_{ZZ}^{ANA} = 7.32 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G_{XY}^{FEA} = 0.441 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G_{XY}^{ANA} = 0.462 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G_{YZ}^{FEA} = 0.771 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G_{XZ}^{ANA} = 0.720 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$G_{XZ}^{FEA} = 0.771 \times 10^6$ (psi)	$G_{YZ}^{ANA} = 0.720 \times 10^6$ (psi)
$\nu_{XY}^{FEA} = 0.416$	$\nu_{XY}^{ANA} = 0.340$
$\nu_{YZ}^{FEA} = 0.317$	$\nu_{YZ}^{ANA} = 0.323$
$\nu_{XZ}^{FEA} = 0.317$	$\nu_{XZ}^{ANA} = 0.323$

CONCLUSION

A numerical approach to predict the effective mechanical properties of a complex EM composite conductor was presented. The procedures of using the FEA model to determine the effective constants were described. The results of the FEA predictions for EM conductors composed of the conducting core and insulating layers, with and without a cooling channel, were illustrated. The results were also compared to the prediction calculated from the analytical models developed previously, which showed a good agreement.

The numerical modeling is critical since it can be adapted for a local-global analysis. The calculated properties can then be used in the machine design by any commercial finite element package. The approach provided a feasible and accurate analysis for an electrical machine with a complex geometry and material contents. The results from the global finite element analysis can be further evaluated at the detail or local level. A detail stress and strain can be examined in the representative volume for potential failure mechanism.

REFERENCES

1. Sun, W. and Tzeng, J., "Effective Mechanical Properties of EM Composite Conductors: analytical and finite element modeling," *Journal of Composite Structures*, Vol. 58, 2002, pp. 411-421
2. Sun, W. and Tzeng, J., "Homogenization Modeling and Effective Mechanical Constants for EM Composite Conductor with Cooling Channel," *Journal of Composite Materials*, in press.
3. Hill, R., "Elastic properties of reinforced solids: Some theoretical principles," *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*. 11 (1963) 357-372.
4. Hashin, Z., "Analysis of composite materials – a survey," *J. Appl. Mech.*, 50 (1983), 481-505.
5. Jones, R.M., "Mechanics of Composite Materials," McGraw-Hill, New York, 1975.